

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT AND MACROECONOMIC TRENDS: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM MENA

DJENNAS Mustapha* & KALAKHI Latifa**

Department of Economics,
University of Tlemcen – Algeria
BP. 226, Tlemcen – Algeria

Abstract

In this paper, the catalyst factors of foreign direct investment inflows in some Middle-East and North Africa countries are examined by applying a Mixed-effect model to a dynamic panel data from 1980 to 2010. The results reveal that government capital Gross national expenditure, trade openness, inflation rate and labor force have robust result. Also a one year lagged values of foreign direct investment is found to have a positive effect on attractiveness of foreign direct investment inflows. Results show also that there is other variables that could be key factors in boosting foreign direct investment attractiveness even if they have not a direct significant effect on foreign direct investment inflows in Middle-East and North Africa. Furthermore, the in-sample selected countries express a high level divergence in terms of conditions needed to create a favorable environment to attract sustainable foreign direct investment projects.

KEYWORDS: FDI - macroeconomic aggregates - panel data - economic growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the new global economic era, foreign direct investment (FDI) is considered as a powerful lever for economic growth in many advanced and emerging economies (Jafari et al, 2011). The increasing growth of FDI has attracted many researches and policymakers who discussed deeply the importance of FDI in economic growth and its important role in the creation of an optimal economic environment. We cannot deny the benefits of FDI especially in the transmission of technology and the spread of experiences acquired from the developed countries. It is assumed that FDI enhance productivity and production growth by increasing competitiveness in economic sectors. Furthermore, FDI have a very considerable impact on capital accumulation (Dutt & Amitava, 1998). FDI inflows contribute in building strong economic links between advanced and developing countries (Erdal & Tatoglu, 2002).

However, Middle-East and North Africa countries (MENA) are not homogenous and represent different economic structures. They have some characteristics that deter FDI from taking place, for instance, political instability, restrictions about FDI to few sectors and preventing the of foreigners to do business with a local partner or implement a joint venture partnership. Other factors contributing to the low performance of MENA countries in attracting FDI include heavy reliance on oil, weak economic structures, high population growth and unemployment rates, the dominance of the state in the economic sector, low economic integration level in the word, underdeveloped financial and capital markets, weak institutions, and low returns rates on human and physical capital (Shirazi et al, 2008). Nevertheless, there has been an increase in the FDI inflows to the MENA region during the last few years, and some countries have played an important role to attract more FDI by pursuing economic policy focused on FDI attractiveness.

The objective of this paper is to examine the determinants of FDI inflows in some MENA countries, which have been remarkably unsuccessful in attracting FDI. For example, Onyeiwu (2000) asserts that the Arab world has continued to receive the least stock of FDI in the world despite its robust resource endowments and oil wealth.

This paper is structured as follows: section 2 provides a review of the relevant literature on FDI. A brief description of the MENA economies and the FDI is given in section 3. Section 4 discusses the methodology and the results of the study. Discussion of the results is presented in section 5. Section 6 concludes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on FDI is very abundant. Most of the studies used multiple theoretical and empirical frameworks in order to achieve appropriate evidences about the relationship between FDI and a range of macroeconomic aggregates (growth, incomes, social welfare, etc.).

The main core literature includes work of Dunning (1993) who tried to explain the FDI inflows by multinational companies. Dunning has classified the variables that affect FDI in three major groups: economic, social or cultural, and political variables. Overall, he concludes that countries that attract FDI of multinational companies have large markets and a high GDP level, low production costs and high political stability.

Root and Ahmed (1978) assembled a set of factors that could affect the FDI movement and concentration in 44 economic, social and political factors having an impact on investment in the industrial sectors in developing countries. Loewendahl et al., (2001) considered that there are more than 20 decisive factors of FDI, and that the literature is still various about the impact of many factors on FDI attractively in the hosted countries. The work of Khachoo and Khan (2012) showed that the investment size depends on the size of the domestic market and also a number of other determinant factors. The study covered a sample of 32 developing countries during the period 1982-2008. They concluded that there is a positive relationship between FDI and the GDP level.

Fayyaz (2012) found the same results through a sample of 57 countries with low and middle income levels between 2000 and 2009. Papanastassiou and Pearce (1990) studied the FDI in the United Kingdom by demonstrating that GDP growth rate is significantly associated with FDI. However, Swedenborg (1979) found that GDP is negatively, and sometimes significantly, related to FDI. In their study, Mellahi et al., (2003) showed that the market size is among the less desirable factors to foreign investors in Oman. Countries may also decide to invest in others countries in order to take advantage of low wage because there are many economists who support the idea that labor costs are a critical factor to attract FDI within countries in period of transition. Nevertheless, some empirical studies found that benefits based on lower wages differences were not a critical determinant of FDI in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (Mody et al., 1998).

Sultan (2013) examines the nature of the relationship between export and FDI in India over the period 1980-2010. Using Johansen co-integration method, he finds a stable long run equilibrium relationship between FDI and export growth. The result of Granger causality based on a vector error correction model (VECM) shows that causality runs from export to FDI inflow direction but not in the opposite direction. However, in the short run, neither exports cause FDI inflows nor FDI inflows cause exports. Asiedu (2002) found that the trade openness and liberalization promote FDI. Scholes and Wolfson (1990) found that a tax increase may enhance the FDI flow.

Moreover, a set of studies found that political instability and corruption have both a negative impact on FDI attractiveness (Alesina and Perotti, 1996; Woodward and Rolfe, 1993; Loree and Guisinger, 1995; Sadig, 2009).

In the case of MENA countries, empirical works on FDI are limited because of data availability for most countries. The study of Onyeiw (2000) reveals that the rate of foreign exchange interest rates and inflation are important factors for FDI flows in some MENA countries.

3. FDI IN MENA COUNTRIES

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD)¹ reported that global FDI inflows grew from an average of 180 billion USD in the period from 1985 to 1995 to 127 trillion USD in 2000, with an increase of 605 percent. Developing countries alone represent 373.3 percent, and MENA countries with an average of 109.1 percent. Furthermore, in 2000 MENA countries FDI inflows represent only 0.4 % of global FDI inflows. However, from 1985 to 2000 the net FDI flows to MENA have positively increased as FDI stock rose from 39.2 to 85.3 billion USD.

In 2000, the Arab world received 1.9 percent of the total FDI outflows coming from developing country. This was slightly higher than developing countries FDI outflows to Europe with the smallest percentage of 0.8 percent.

Despite the fact that these statistics of FDI outflows are very modest at a global level, they are particularly important for some MENA countries. As it was mentioned above, more than the third of these FDI outflows had another MENA member as a destination. For instance, oil importing countries in MENA such as Egypt, Morocco, Jordan, and Tunisia heavily depend on these intra-regional FDI flows to finance their infrastructure projects. Furthermore, most of the FDI outflows in the region are concentrated among just a few countries. In 2010, more than 83% of FDI inflows in the MENA region were concentrated in 7 countries (Figure 1): Saudi Arabia (41.4%), Egypt (9.4%), Qatar (8.1%), Lebanon (7.3%), United Arab Emirates (5.8%), Libya (5.6%), and Iran (5.3%). This distribution is not only particular to 2010 but also of the whole previous decade where Saudi Arabia received 29% of all FDI inflows, followed by the UAE with 16.2% and Egypt with 11%.

Figure 2 shows, the main countries share of FDI inflows corresponding to oil-producing countries. Nevertheless, the majority of the other larger oil-producing countries (Algeria, Libya, and Kuwait) receive very low FDI relative to expected levels of foreign investment.

The FDI concentration inflows in MENA is generally directed towards petroleum and natural resources activities, which cause a certain volatility in investment because of the vulnerability of these commodities to price changes. Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Oman, Qatar, Kuwait, Libya and Yemen are continuing to receive large investments parts in

¹ UNCTAD <http://unctad.org/en/Pages/Home.aspx>

hydrocarbon sector while Bahrain, United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia and Lebanon received investments in more diverse sectors such as tourism, banking, telecommunication, manufacturing and construction. Many of these inflows are the result of mergers, acquisitions and privatization.

4. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

4.1. Data and variables

In this study, we use a dynamic model of panel data with 5 MENA countries (Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, Egypt and Turkey). The time period range from 1980 to 2010. Data are collected mainly from the UNCTAD² and the World Bank³. Following the previous relevant literature, we have tried to include the main variables affecting FDI. Some specific variables to MENA are also added to the set of main variables. Because of missing values, we were constrained to restrict our time series data between 1980 and 2010:

GDP growth rate: one of the main used indicators in making investment decision. Its increase contributes in the country. Overall, it is assumed that there is a positive relationship between the GDP growth rate and the FDI flows. *External debt:* debt may be a result of non appropriate macroeconomic policies that do not encourage FDI. The debt service burdens limited the ability of countries to provide basic infrastructure. It is expected that the increase in the debt ratio limits the FDI inflow in a country. *Government capital expenditure:* government spending is a complement to private investment, especially when the capital expenditure are invested in infrastructure projects as roads, transportation, telecommunication, water and electricity. Therefore, the increase of government investment may attract the FDI flows. *Oil rent:* it represent the difference between the value of crude oil production at world's prices and total costs of production. It is expected to have a positive significant relationship between oil rent and FDI. *Trade openness:* the openness of an economy is measured by the ratio of trade to GDP (exports plus imports divided by GDP). This ratio can be an attractive factor for FDI. We expect a positive link between economic openness and FDI. The other variables used in this study are exports of goods and services, inflation rate, official exchange rate, and total labor force. The nature of the relationship between these variables and FDI is rather

² <http://unctad.org/en/Pages/Home.aspx>

³ www.worldbank.org/

divergent on the different previous studies. It is highly dependent on the context of the study, time horizon, econometric tools, etc.

4.2. Econometric methodology

In our regression analysis, we introduce a change in the basic regression equation estimated by Arellano-Bond which takes in account lagged values on the dependent variable (in our case, FDI in $t-1$ is included as an explanatory variable). This estimator is included in the model in order to assess the impact of the previous FDI flows on the present value.

In addition, we consider two component of the panel data analysis, the Fixed-Effect model (FE) and the Random-Effect model (RE). These models incorporate both inter-temporal dynamics and individual differences, which provides better control for the effects of missing or unobserved variables. They are useful in a wide variety of research fields in social sciences.

4.2.1. The Mixed-effect models

In statistics, panel data with Mixed-effect models are commonly used. Usually, these models contain the two fundamental components mentioned above. Mixed-effect models are particularly useful because of their advantage to deal with missing values, and for this reason they are often preferred over more traditional approaches.

From our data, the regression equation in a Mixed-effect model can be represented as:

$$Y_{it} = \gamma Y_{i,t-1} + \beta X_{it} + uZ_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y_{it} is the dependent variable where i is the entity and t the time (FDI for country i at time t)

$Y_{i,t-1}$ is the previous FDI value in $t-1$ (FDI for country i at time $t-1$)

β is an unknown vector of fixed effects

u is an unknown vector of random effects with mean 0 and variance-covariance matrix σ_u

ϵ is an unknown vector of random errors with mean 0 and variance σ_ϵ

X and Z are known design matrices relating the y observations to β and u respectively.

Therefore, in a Mixed-effect model, there are two common assumptions made about the entity specific effect. The FE assumption is that the entities specific effect is correlated with the exogenous variables, and the RE assumption is that the entities specific effects are uncorrelated with the exogenous variables.

4.2.2. Fixed-Effect regression model

In panel data, the fixed effects estimator (or the within effect) is used to refer to an estimator for the coefficients in the regression model. If we assume FE, we impose time independent effects for each entity that are possibly correlated with the regressors:

Therefore, the regression equation of the FE models is:

$$Y_{it} = \gamma Y_{it-1} + bX_{i,t} + \alpha_i + u_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

In addition to the previous component in equation (1), $\alpha_i (i=1 \dots n)$ is the unknown intercept for each entity (n entity-specific intercepts). X_{it} represents one independent variable. b is the coefficient for that independent variable. u_{it} is the error term.

Therefore, FE models control for, or partial out, the effects of time-invariant variables with time-invariant effects (Allison, 2009).

4.2.3. Random-Effect regression model

In random effects regression, one or more of the regressors are assumed to be random variables that come from an underlying distribution that may be known or not. When random effects are included in a model, then the variation associated with the random effects can be taken into account. In RE models, we assume that there is no fixed effects:

$$Y_{i,t} = Y_{i,t-1} + \beta X_{i,t} + \alpha + u_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

In addition to the previous component, $u_{i,t}$ is the previous *Between-entity* error, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the *Within-entity* error. β is the coefficient for the independent variable under RE conditions.

In the next section we demonstrate that the random effects are preferred for fixed effects in our panel data. Generalized least squares method is used in the random effects approach to provide the best linear unbiased estimate.

Table 1. Regression on the dependent variable FDI_t

		FE regression model	RE regression model
FDI_{t-1} (FDI in the previous year)	Coef.	0.484707	0.566234
	Std. Err.	0.104755	0.092557
	t	4.63	6.12
	P> t	0.000	0.000
Government capital expenditure	Coef.	1.4E-07	1.06E-07
	Std. Err.	3.77E-08	3.25E-08
	t	3.71	3.26
	P> t	0.000	0.001
Oil rents	Coef.	-37.7226	-165.056
	Std. Err.	227.3697	125.5446
	t	-0.17	-1.31
	P> t	0.868	0.189
External debt	Coef.	4.04E-07	2.45E-07

	Std. Err.	4.1E-07	3.08E-07
	t	0.99	0.79
	P> t	0.326	0.427
Official exchange rate	Coef.	23.85508	-6.63805
	Std. Err.	84.58874	52.65977
	t	0.28	-0.13
	P> t	0.778	0.900
Trade openness	Coef.	21933.01	23424.34
	Std. Err.	9969.792	8177.629
	t	2.2	2.86
	P> t	0.029	0.004
GDP growth rate	Coef.	5.724992	-3.27836
	Std. Err.	234.7502	232.3712
	t	0.02	-0.01
	P> t	0.981	0.989
Exports of goods and services	Coef.	-2.04E-07	-1.1E-07
	Std. Err.	1.52E-07	1.32E-07
	t	-1.34	-0.87
	P> t	0.183	0.387
Inflation rate	Coef.	-117.796	-191.718
	Std. Err.	70.47669	46.5921
	t	-1.67	-4.11
	P> t	0.097	0.000
Total labor force	Coef.	0.000384	0.000148
	Std. Err.	0.000225	5.94E-05
	t	1.71	2.49
	P> t	0.090	0.013

Significant coefficients are in bold character

4.2.4. Hausman test result

After running the two regression frameworks, we must apply a Hausman test to assess whether the FE or the RE model is more appropriate for our panel data. In the case of any fundamental difference in the FE regression, this can be linked to the extent to which the entities (countries) characteristics are correlated with the regressors. But when we consider FE regression, then the time invariant component is supposed to be correlated with the regressors.

The Hausman test is a statistical hypothesis test used to evaluate the consistency of an estimator when compared to an alternative, less efficient, estimator which is already known to be consistent. Hence, in panel data models, it is used to differentiate between FE and RE. In this case, RE model is more appropriate under the null hypothesis due to higher efficiency, while under the alternative FE model is at least consistent and thus preferred:

	H₀ true	H₁ true
b estimator under FE conditions	Consistent	Consistent
β estimator under RE conditions	Efficient	Inconsistent

The Hausman statistic is distributed as χ^2 and is computed as (Hausman, 1978):

$$H = (b_c - \beta_e)'(V_c - V_e)^{-1}(b_c - \beta_e) \quad (4)$$

Where:

- b_c is the coefficient vector from the consistent estimator
- β_e is the coefficient vector from the efficient estimator
- V_c is the covariance matrix of the consistent estimator
- V_e is the covariance matrix of the efficient estimator

Results of the χ^2 test are presented in the following table. The p value of the χ^2 is equal to 0.297.

Table 2. Hausman statistic χ^2

	b (FE)	β (RE)	$(b - \beta)$ Difference	$\text{sqrt}(\text{diag}(V_b - V_\beta))$ S.E.
FDI _{t-1}	0.4847069	0.5662338	-0.081527	0.0490577
gne	1.40E-07	1.06E-07	3.40E-08	1.91E-08
oilrent	-37.7226	-165.0555	127.3329	189.5668
exdebt	4.04E-07	2.45E-07	1.59E-07	2.70E-07
extra	23.85508	-6.638048	30.49312	66.19821
tropen	21933.01	23424.34	-1491.331	5702.906
gdpg	5.724992	-3.278363	9.003355	33.33616
exp	-2.04E-07	-1.14E-07	-8.98E-08	7.62E-08
infl	-117.7957	-191.7183	73.92267	52.87854
pop	0.0003837	0.000148	0.0002358	0.0002168

Since the estimated p value of the χ^2 test exceeds the critical value at 5% degree of freedom (the number of potentially endogenous variables), the result is to accept the null hypothesis of no endogeneity.

According to Allison (2009), in a RE model, the unobserved variables are assumed to be uncorrelated with (or, more strongly, statistically independent of) all the observed variables. That assumption will often be wrong but, for the reasons that standard errors may be very high in FE regression, RE lets us assess effects for time-invariant variables. For this reason, we might interpret this result as strong evidence that we cannot reject the null hypothesis, and this is why RE model are more appropriate to our data.

4.2.5. Pesaran cross dependence test

The Pesaran test is a simple test of measuring error cross-section dependence in panel data models. The proposed tests is based on average of pair-wise correlation coefficients of the OLS residuals from the individual regressions in the panel, and can be used to test for cross section dependence (Pesaran, 2004).

The Pesaran test is widely inspired from the proposed Lagrange multiplier (LM) test statistic for fixed N and T ($\rightarrow \infty$) by (Breusch, 1980):

$$LM = T \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{p}_{ij}^2 \quad (5)$$

Where \hat{p}_{ij} is the sample estimate of the pairwise correlation of the residuals:

$$\hat{p}_{ij} = \hat{p}_{ji} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \hat{u}_{it} \hat{p}_{jt}}{(\sum_{t=1}^T \hat{u}_{it}^2)^{1/2} (\sum_{t=1}^T \hat{u}_{jt}^2)^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

Where \hat{u}_{it} is the estimate of u in (1). LM is asymptotically distributed as χ^2 with $N(N - 1)/2$ degrees of freedom under the null hypothesis of interest. Then, the Pesaran proposed test is as follow:

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N - 1)}} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{p}_{ij} \right) \quad (7)$$

According to the test, under the null hypothesis there is no cross-sectional dependence in panel data. Our results give us a Pesaran’s test of cross sectional independence equal to 0.956, with a probability of 0.3391. With such probability (higher than 5%), we should accept the null hypothesis and conclude that our model does not represent autocorrelations between residuals.

5. DISCUSSION: FDI DETERMINANTS IN MENA

As all the existing literature on FDI, the results indicate that there are variables connected positively with FDI (positive correlation), namely previous FDI inflows (one year lagged values), government spending, trade openness and labor force. Other variables are associated with negative significant relationship to FDI such as inflation rate. However, even if there is not significant relationship between some variables and FDI, there could be a significant interpretation for the nature of the links.

With the Arellano-Bond approach, the results indicate that the evolution of FDI in MENA is constantly increasing, because we found a strong significant relationship between the value of FDI in a year t and the same value in the year $t+1$. Then, the tendency is a positive growth of FDI in MENA countries.

Results show that the relationship between the government spending and FDI is strongly positive in MENA countries. This may indicate that some governments in MENA countries still play a leading role in the development process of FDI. The raising of expenditures affects positively the climate of attracting investment outflows by, for example, reducing the corruption, facilitating administrative procedures in relation with investment projects.

In terms of the trade openness, we found a significant positive relationship with FDI. Therefore, this can be seen as a growing need in MENA to achieve more openness in trade, in markets and financial inflows in order to attract FDI to this region. Indeed, between 1980 and 2010, MENA countries witnessed very important structural changes mainly due to the new adopted reforms to attract new investments opportunities.

The relationship between inflation and FDI is negative, statistically significant and robust. In terms of policy recommendations, this finding suggests that if well implemented, the targeting policy of inflation can be a necessary factor to policymakers in MENA countries in their competition to attract more FDI. Therefore, it makes more sense that foreign investors may desire more stable economy for profitability and easy earnings flow under macroeconomic stability in MENA.

The labor force growth rate has a positive and significant effect on FDI. For the most countries, the increase in the labor affects positively the FDI leading to a situation where the supply exceed the demand in the labor market. This will encourage investors to implement their project under such conditions (reduced costs of wages).

The results also show an inverse but weak relationship between the GDP growth rate and FDI because of the low FDI inflows to MENA countries in the considered period in this study, as well as the high degree of volatility in inflows investment to MENA. Other factors may also justify this insignificant negative relationship, for instance, the transfer of huge amounts of capitals from countries hosting investment projects outward (to investors' origin country or to other more attractive countries), and the lack of diversification in MENA economies characterized by high concentration levels of FDI in one sector (hydrocarbon sector in Algeria, tourism sector in Tunisia, Morocco, Egypt and Turkey). Such factors are likely contributing in shaping an ambiguous relationship between GDP growth rate and FDI in MENA economies.

Our analysis give us a negative but not significant relationship between exchange rate and FDI in MENA countries. This is quite different compared to some works, because in a wide part of literature, it is argued that exchange rate is one of the main factors that influence FDI activity. According to (Goldberg and Kolstad, 1994), exchange rates can influence both the total amount of FDI that takes place and the allocation of this investment spending across a range of countries. Indeed, when a currency depreciates, the exchange rate movement has two potential implications for FDI. First, it reduces the level of wages and production costs relative to those of foreign counterparts in a hosting country. All else equal, under a currency depreciation, the country enhance a competitive advantage or attractiveness as a location for receiving productive capacity investments. Therefore, the exchange rate depreciation improves the overall rate of return to foreigners contemplating an overseas investment project in a country.

When looking to table 1, our study cannot define properly the direct correspondence between exports and FDI, probably because of the presence of some positive and negative compensating effects and/or lagged-value effects. This outcome is unsuccessful because we are not able to give a decisive direct answer to the question about the relationship between these two macroeconomic aggregates. However, even if our analysis does not clarify completely the correct relationship between exportations and FDI, it may give a channel of interpretation. It seems that FDI in MENA are an initial condition for a more complete economic involvement in their markets.

Figures 3 and 4 give a presentation of our in-sample countries in terms of FDI, GDP growth rate and inflation. It seems that Algeria is the most country positioned in an unfavorable situation with low levels of FDI and GDP growth rate. Morocco and Tunisia are in a slightly better position with higher levels of FDI inflows, acceptable GDO growth rate and relatively low inflation rates. Turkey and Egypt are part of MENA countries characterized indeed by high levels of inflation but also very important inflows of FDI. Turkey nevertheless remains the example to follow in this group of countries in terms of FDI attractiveness policy.

Figure 3. FDI and GDP growth in MENA
(Average 1980-2010)

Figure 4. FDI and inflation in MENA
(Average 1980-2010)

6. CONCLUSION

This paper evaluates the robustness between inward FDI inflow and various economic indicators in MENA. It is an attempt of analyzing the main determinants of FDI inflows in some MENA countries, namely Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, Egypt, and Turkey between 1980 and 2010.

The nature and the direction of the effects of our selected determinants on FDI may be different in comparison to other studies, because under some specific conditions, a variable may affect FDI both positively and negatively. In the existing literature on FDI, a various combination of these determinants as explanatory variables have been used. However, there a large number of researchers and policymakers who claim that due to the absence of a consensus on

a theoretical framework to guide empirical work on FDI, there is no widely accepted set of explanatory variables that can be considered as the absolute determinants of FDI.

By applying Mixed-effect models on a panel data to a sample of cross-sectional data covering the five MENA countries, the empirical results show that FDI can be explained in terms of GDP growth rate, government capital expenditure, trade openness, inflation and labor force. Overall, results tell us that countries that express more attractiveness of FDI are those with a constantly growing economy characterized by high level of labor supply, low country risk and high economic stability, and high levels of financial commitments from the previous earnings from the past FDI projects. This seems to be an appropriate description of the countries that show acceptable competitive advantage in attracting FDI.

To conclude it can be said that MENA countries need to reinforce their infrastructure facilities, improve the quality of its service, liberalize its local and global investment policy further and last but not the least to maintain macroeconomic and political stability to improve its inward FDI performance and so to become an attractive destination for foreign investors.

7. REFERENCES

- Alesina, A., and Perotti, R. (1996). “Reducing Budget Deficits”. *Swedish Economic Policy Review*. Vol. 3(1), pp.135-138
- Allison, P.D. (2009). *Fixed Effects Regression Models (Quantitative Applications in the Social Sciences)*. Sage edition, April 22, 2009.
- Asiedu, E., (2002), “On the Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment to Developing Countries: Is Africa Different?” *World Development*. Vol. 30(1), pp.107-119.
- Breusch, T., and Pagan, A. (1980). “The Lagrange multiplier test and its application to model specification in econometrics”. *Review of Economic Studies*. Vol. 47: 239-253.
- Dunning, J.H., (1993). *Multinational Enterprises and the Global Economy*. Reading, Addison-Wesley Publ. Co. New York.
- Dutt, A. (1998). “Globalization, FDI and southern Growth”. *Economic effects of globalization*, pp.45-96.
- Erdal, F., and Tatoglu, E. (2002). “Locational Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment in an Emerging Market Economy: Evidence from Turkey”. *Multinational Business Review*. Vol. 10, pp.21-27.
- Fayyaz H. (2012). “Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment Flows to Developing Countries”. *SBP Research Bulletin*. Vol. 8, No. 1, 2012.
- Goldberg L.S., and Kolstad, C.D., (1994). “Foreign Direct Investment, Exchange Rate Variability and Demand Uncertainty”. *NBER Working Paper* No. 4815. Issued in August 1994.
- Hausman, J.A., (1978). “Specification tests in econometrics”. *Econometrica*. Vol. 46: pp.1251-1271
- Khachoo, A., and Khan, M.I., (2012). “Determinants of FDI Inflows to Developing Countries: A Panel Data Analysis”. *MPRA Paper* No. 37278, http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/37278/1/MPRA_paper_37278.pdf
- Loewendahl, H., and Loewendahl, E., (2001). “Turkey’s Performance in Attracting Foreign Direct Investment: Implications in EU Enlargement”. Working Paper N°8, *European Network of Economic Policy research Institutes*, pp.1-48.
- Loree, D., and Guisinger, S., (1995). “Policy and non-Policy Determinants of U.S. Foreign Direct Investment”. *Journal of International Business Studies*. Vol. 26(2): pp.281-299.
- Mellahi, K., Guermat, C., Fryneas, J.G., and Al-Bortmani, H., (2003). “Motives for Foreign Direct Investment in Oman”. *Thunderbird International Business Review*. Vol. 45(4): pp.431-446.

- Mody, A., and Wheeler, D. (1992). "International investment location decisions: the case of U S firms". *Journal of International Economics*. Vol. 33: pp.57-76.
- Mody, A., Dasgupta, S., and Sinha, S. (1998). "Japanese Multinationals in Asia: Drivers and Attractors". *Oxford Development Studies*. Vol. 27:2, pp.149-164.
- Onyeiwu, S., (2000). "Foreign direct investment, capital outflows and economic development in the Arab World". *Journal of Development and economic Policies*. Vol. 2(2), pp.27-57.
- Papanastassiou, M., and Pearce, R.D., (1990). "Host Country Characteristics and the Sourcing Behaviour of U.K Manufacturing Industry". University of Reading, Department of Economics. *Discussion Papers in International Investment and Business Studies*, Series B. Vol. 2. No. 140.
- Pesaran, M.H., (2004). "General diagnostic tests for cross section dependence in panels". Cesifo Working paper no. 1229, category 10: empirical and theoretical methods.http://www.cesifo-group.de/portal/page/portal/DocBase_Content/WP/WP-CESifo_Working_Papers/wp-cesifo-2004/wp-cesifo-2004-07/cesifo1_wp1229.pdf
- Root, F.R., and Ahmed, A.A., (1979). "Empirical Determinants of Manufacturing Direct Foreign Investment in Developing Countries". *Economic Development and Cultural Change*. Vol.27, Issue 4, pp.751-767.
- Sadig, A., (2009). "The Effects of Corruption on FDI Inflows". *Cato Journal*. Vol. 2: pp.267-294.
- Samimi, J.A., Monfared, M., Moghaddasi, R., and Azizi, K. (2011). "Political Stability and FDI in OIC Countries". *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*. Vol. 1(1), pp.18-23.
- Scholes, M., and Wolfson, M.A., (1990). "The effects of changes in tax law on corporates reorganization activity". *Journal of Business*. Vol. 63: pp.141-164.
- Shirazi, A., Rodrigues, G., and Karnik, A., (2008). "Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment in MENA countries: an empirical analysis". First International Business Conference. University of Wollongong. <http://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1168&context=dubaipapers>
- Sultan, Z.A., (2013). "A Causal Relationship between FDI Inflows and Export: The Case of India". *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*. Vol.4 (2): pp.1-9.
- Swedenborg, B., (1979). "The Multinational operations of Swedish Firms: An Analysis of Determinants and Effects". *Stockholm: Industriens Utredningsinstitut*. Vol. 1(1), pp.18-23.
- Woodward, D., and Rolfe, R., (1993). "The Location of Export Oriented Foreign Direct Investment in the Caribbean Basin". *Journal of International Business Studies*. Vol. 24(1): pp.121-144.